

NOTE: CERAMICS COLLECTED BY W.M. SUMNER IN 1967-69

CHRONOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION OF SITES PROVIDED BY ANDREW WILLIAMSON ON OCTOBER 30, 1969.

KUR RIVER VALLEY SASSANIAN AND ISLAMIC POTTERY

Justification for the chronological classification of sites.

Period .S. c.-800 A.D.

Type pottery: unglazed, burnished, and slipped with distinctive profiles. Type sites: mounds above Nagsh-i-Rustam, Qasr-i-Abu Nasr spoil heap. Dating: Pas Takht IV has no associated glazed pottery. Pottery found in abundance at Qasr-i-Abu Nasr in early Islamic and late Sassanian context. (Met Bul Nov. 1933 sect 2 p.39ff). Terminal date: Exceedingly rare on the surface of Istakhr and in Schmidt's trenches which have abundant very early polychrome glazed ware (introduced c. 800 A.D.).

Period .I. c. 800-1150 A.D.

Type pottery: splashed ware, c.f. Sirjan kiln ware, thin yellow glaze, spinnach green c.f. Nishapur. Type sites: N. 648, Istakhr, both of which have a wide range of polychrome glazed ware and practically no 'Seljuc' frit pottery (very common after c. 1150). Initial date: Polychrome glaze appears at Siraf c. 800 A.D. This is probably the most discrete period since its beginning and end are determined by important technological innovations. It is also best represented at Siraf.

Period .2. c. 1150-1500 A.D.

Type pottery: 'Seljuc' frit body, lustre on frit body, Chekiang celadon, flange and hammer rims on body c.f. Siraf IV. Dating: Earliest frit body c.1150 (the earliest piece with a painted date is 1179 A.D.). A large number of painted dates on lustre pots from 1179-1339 A.D. Chekiang celadon introduced Siraf IV. 15 c. A.D. material from Siraf IV and the pots set in the roof of 'The house of the mosque' at Kilwa (East Africa) (Azania 1 p23-4, pLIXI) and the upper levels of the Takht Pas.. Art historical treatment in Ars Islamica v.2 pl55ff. However, a mihrab from Abarquh in the Shiraz museum carries the date 809 A.H. (1406 A.D.) under a very glassy glaze. (Athar-e Iran vl part2 p336-7). Its condition could be a result of not being buried, or it might not be as old as the painted date indicates. The pattern and style of decoration are unlike any of the pottery listed above. I am studying the problem. This period could be subdivided into two at about 1350, that is befor the introduction of Siraf IV pottery, or Chekiang celadon.

50
ear
eriod

50
ear
eriod

Period .3.

c. 1500-

Type pottery: late Persian blue and white from Kerman etc., glossy surfaced turquoise glazed ware, Japanese export porcelain.

Dating: Pottery absent from Siraf IV but present in small later deposits at Siraf site g. Painted dates on late blue and white of 16-18c. A.D.

Japanese export porcelain from 19 c. A.D. onwards.

Because of the lack of stratigraphically excavated sites in the area this whole framework and especially the later periods must be treated with caution.

C = INDEX CARD
 P = PAINTED SHERDS
 O = OTHER - FRIT, SGRAFFIATO, MOULDED AND GLAZED WARES.

SITE	PERIOD	SITE	PERIOD	SITE	PERIOD
100 c	3	207	S	316B O	1
102 c	3	209	S,1	318	3
103 c	3	210	S	319 c	2,3
104 c	2	212	1,2	321 c P	1,2,3
105 c	2	213	S,1,2,3	321A	1
106 c	2,3	214	S,2	321B	1,2
108 c	3	215	2,1,2	321C	2
109 c	3	216	1,2,3	324 c P	2,3
112 c	3	217	S	330 c	1,3
113 c P	1,2	218	S	332	2
114 c	3	219	3	336 c	2,3
116 c	3	220	1	339 c	3(?)
117 c	1	229	3	345 c P	2
118 c	3	231	discard	352 c	1,2
119 c	3	234	discard	357 c	S
122 c	2,3	235	discard	358 c	3
127 c	1,3	301	3	365 c	2,3
129 c	S,1,2	302 c	3	366 c P	2
133 c	3	304A	3	367 c	1,2
		306 c	3	369 P	S,1,2
200	S,2	308	3,2	369B P	1,2
204	S	312 c	1,3	369C P	1,2
206	3	313	1,2	369D P	1

*Now listed as 130

SITE	PERIOD	SITE	PERIOD	SITE	PERIOD
370 C	2	411	2,3	548 C	3
371 P	1,2	418 C	3	549 C P	2,3
371A P	1,2	419	3	550 C P O	3
371D	2,3	500 C P	2	554 C P	3
372 C	2	501B C	2	557 P	2,3
373 C	3	502 C P	2,3	558	2,3
374 C	2	504 C P	3	559 C P	3,1,S
375 P	1,2	505 C	2	559A P	S,1
375A P	1,2	507 C P	3,2	560 P	3
375C P	2	513 C P	1	562 P	1
376 C P	S,1	514 C P	S,1	563	2,3
384 C P	2,3	519 C P	1,2	564 C P	3,2
390 C P	3	521 C	3	564A	3
391 C P	S,1,2,3	523 C	1,3	564B C	2,3
392 P O	1,2,3	526 C	3	564C	3
393 C P	2,3	530	1	566 C	1
394	3	531 C P	S,3	567 C P	1,2
397 C P	1,2	536 C P	3	569	(3?) discard
397A P	1,2	537B C	3,S	570 C P	3
398	2,3	543 C	3	571	2,3
399 C P	2,3	544 C	3	573	1
3A5 C	2	546	S	574 C	3
3X1 P	2	547	S	588	1

SITE	PERIOD	SITE	PERIOD	SITE	PERIOD
590 C P	1,3	5S0	3	668	2,3
591	3	5S1 C	S,2	668A P	2,3 P
593 P	1,2,3	5S5 C P	2,3	669	2
595 C	1,3	5S6	S	674 C	3
597 C	3	5T8 C	1	676	3
5A1 C	discard	5T9 P	2,S	678 P	1
5B1 C P	3	5U1	3	684 C P	3
5B4	1	5V0	S	691	S
5B5	discard	5W2	discard	Kumi Qalam	1,2,3,
5B8	3	5W9 C	3	713	S
5B9 C P	1	5X2	S(?)	722	S
5C0 C	1	5X8	(3?) discard	738	2
5C1(B)	2,3	5Y6 C P	1	803	1,2 P
5D0	2	607 C P	S,3	804	S,1
5E1 C	1,2	616 C P	1	806	1
5E2 P	2,3	633 P	3	807 P	1
5H0 C	3	634 C P	3,2	810	1,2
5J2 C P	S,2,3	638 P	3	816	2,3
5J9 C	1	639 C P	2	817 P	1,2
5K0	S	641	1	819 P	1,2 P
5K8 C	2,3	643 P	3	821	S
5N4 C	3	644 C P	1,2,3	827	1
5N7 P	2,3	655	2	828	S
5Q9	S & (1?)	657 C	2,3	8X1	3
5R6 C	1	660 C	3	8X2 P P	1

SITE PERIOD SITE PERIOD SITE PERIOD

8X4 1

8X6 2,3

V02 C P DISCARD

Numbers : 231 (3?) discard; 234 discard; 3E0 discard; 333 discard; were left off of list
5L9 3; 5V5 3; 5V4 discard

~~AV4~~ ~~5H~~ ~~UNLISTED PAINTED SHERDS~~ ~~SITES WITH~~ UNLISTED SITE WITH PAINTED AND OTHER SHERDS - NO
 NUMBERED SHERDS WITHOUT CARDS AND NOT ON LIST.

375 B
 375 X
 376 A
 396 A
 396 X
 396 General.
 398 A Other

501
~~501~~
 534
 551 Other
~~551~~
 565
 572 Other
 577
 586

5A2
 5C2
 5C5
 5C8
 5F3
 5F3
 5G2
 5H4

632
 645 A
 645 B
 646
 648 A
 648 B
 665
 ISTAKHR.
 KARATUUI?

PREDOMINANTLY PAINTED SHERDS WITHOUT NO'S.
COULD YOU PLEASE SUPPLY NUMBERS FOR THESE SITES. -
MARKED SHERDS - NO NO'S. PLEASE SUPPLY.
EXCEPT FOR ISTAKHR. IF THEY
EXIST.

ISTAKHR.
IST B.
IST C
IST D
IST F
IST G
IST H
IST J.
IST MECHT'S HUT.

JAMALABAD.

CHARTEHAR B.

SALAL.

Q. KHAR B.

RAHNAU

T. SHAR KH.

- MARU DASHT - SASANIAN + ISLAMIC SITES
AREA IN HA.

SITE	AREA (HA.)	SITE	AREA	SITE	Area	SITE	Area
100	0.1	374	3.7	562	1.3	641	0.1
102	2.8	375	6.0	563	1.1	643A	0.4
105	0.6	376	0.3	564	4.0	644	1.5
108	1.0	384	6.0	567	1.6	657	3.0
109	1.9	391	25.0	573	0.8	660	0.5
112	0.3	392	15.0	588	0.4	668	15.0
113	0.5	393	1.8	590	1.3	669	8.0
114	0.2	394	6.0	593	6.0	674	0.9
116	2.8	397	2.0	595	1.2	678	0.7
117	0.3	398	0.6	597	1.2	684	4.5
122	caves	399	18.0	5B1	4.0	691	4.2
127	7.0	500	6.0	5C0	0.9	722	3.0
302	1.0	501	2.0	5C1B	0.3	330	0.1
306	1.0	504	2.0	5E1	1.4	558	0.6
312	0.6	507	1.5	5E2	2.0	5B4	0.6
313	2.8	513	0.4	5J2	0.6	676	1.7
316	4.2	514	0.6	5J9	1.1	571	6.0
318	12.0	519	1.9	5K0	0.5	5V5	0.2
319	16.8	521	4.0	5F8	2.0	5S0	1.3
321	8.0	523	1.5	5U1	1.0	5B8	0.6
324	8.0	526	0.1	5W9	0.4	304.A	1.0
336	3.5	530	cave	5Y6	0.9	5N4	6.0
352	2.0	531	0.8	607	2.0	5H0	3.0
365	3.2	544	1.0	616	3.0	308	1.4
366	0.7	548	0.5	638	2.6		
369	0.8	554	1.1	639	0.4		
373	3.5	559	2.0	634	0.4		